

Effects of Ion-pairing on the Acid and Base Hydrolysis of Oxalato Pentaammine Cobalt (III) Complex

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The rate influencing effects of anions on the acid and base hydrolysis of oxalato pentaammine Cobalt(III) have been examined. Both SO_4^{2-} and HSO_4^- accelerate the rate of aquation of the complex through formation of the reactive ion-pairs, $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+]\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}]\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ respectively. HSO_4^- ion has also been found to act as an acid as well as ion-pairing ligand in catalysing the aquation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}$.

The base hydrolysis of the oxalato complex has been studied in the presence of CH_3CO_2^- , CO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} , and PO_4^{3-} . Acetate ion has no influence while CO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} , and PO_4^{3-} retard the reaction in the sequence: $\text{CO}_3^{2-} < \text{SO}_4^{2-} < \text{PO}_4^{3-}$.

THE rates of aquation of halopentaamminecobalt(III)¹⁻³ and halopentaamminechromium(III)⁴⁻⁶ cations (except $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CrF}^{2+}$) are accelerated in the presence of anions. The rate accelerating effect of polyvalent anions on such reactions has been observed to be more pronounced as compared to that of the univalent anions¹. The observed anion catalysis of the aquation reactions of the complexes cited above has been attributed to the following facts: (1) the cationic complexes form outersphere ion-pairs with the added anions, and (2) the ion-pairs so formed react much faster than the corresponding free complex ions. Noteworthy is the fact that anions like sulphate and pyrophosphate which strongly catalyse the aquation of chloro, bromo, and iodopentaammine-Cr(III) complexes have been found to exert no accelerating effect on the rate of aquation of fluoropentaammine-Cr(III)⁶. This very striking observation led Jones *et al.*⁶ to suggest that Cr-F bond fission is less important in the aquation reaction of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CrF}^{2+}$ cation. On the other hand, the observed sequence of the reactivities of the ion-pairs, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{MXA}^{(2-n)+}$ ($\text{M}^{3+} = \text{Cr}^{3+}$ or Co^{3+} , $\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , or I^- , and A^{n-} is a polyvalent anion), and the free complex cations, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{MX}^{2+}$, is consistent with the rate limiting M-X bond breaking.

In contrast to the acid hydrolysis reactions, the base hydrolysis reactions of halopentaamminecobalt(III)^{3,7} as well as bromo and fluoropentaamminechromium(III)⁸ complexes have been reported to be retarded by anions. Polyvalent anions retard the reactions to a greater extent than the univalent anions. Monk *et al.*³ have recently examined the retarding influence of several dicarboxylate and sulphate ions on the rate of base hydrolysis of acetatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex. Their results indicate that the rates of alkaline hydrolysis of the ion-pairs, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoAc}^{2+}$. A^{2-} , decrease in the order of increasing stability of the ion-pairs.

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This paper describes the study of the influence of the anions on the rates of aquation and base hydrolysis of oxalato pentaamminecobalt(III) complex. It was aimed to examine the possibilities of outer sphere ion-pair formation by $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+$ and $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}$ and estimate the catalytic activities of various anions on the acid and base hydrolysis of this complex. It was hoped that the results obtained might be useful in elucidating the nature of bond breaking involved in the acid and base hydrolysis of the oxalato complex.

Experimental

$[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was prepared by the method of Saffir and Taube⁹. *Anal.* Calc. for $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$; Co, 13.63; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, 20.4. Found: Co, 13.6; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, 20.3%.

All solutions were prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of decinormal permanganate was standardised against B.D.H.(A.R.) sodium oxalate which was previously dried at 105° for 3 hr. Baker Analysed Reagent perchloric acid and reagent grade sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were used to maintain acidity and ionic strength of the reaction medium. All other chemicals were of B.D.H.(A.R.) quality. Dowex 50W-X8 resin in acid form was used for all ion exchange experiments.

Kinetics

The solutions of desired composition were prepared in 100 ml volumetric flasks and equilibrated in the thermostat. After thermal equilibrium was reached, a known weight of the complex was transferred into the reaction flask and the volume was immediately made up with distilled water equilibrated at the same temperature. 10 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at convenient time intervals, the reaction was quenched by diluting with an equal volume of ice cold water (for acid hydrolysis) or

with ice cold standard perchloric acid (for base hydrolysis). The solution was then shaken with a few grams of Dowex 50W-X8 resin in acid form till the supernatant liquid was colourless indicating complete exchange of cobalt(III) complexes into the resin phase. It was then filtered through a well packed bed of glass wool. The resin was washed with distilled water. The oxalic acid content of the combined filtrate and resin washings was estimated by $N/50$ $KMnO_4$ in the conventional way. The pseudo-first-order rate constants for acid and base hydrolysis reactions were calculated from the least squares slopes of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. time plots where V_t and V_∞ stand for the permanganate titre value at time t and for complete reaction respectively. V_∞ was calculated from the weight of the complex and was corrected for the solvent blank. All calculations were performed with an IBM 1130 computer.

Results and Discussion

Acid Hydrolysis

The acid hydrolysis of oxalatopentaamminecobalt (III) complex has been studied at 66.1° and $0.3M$ ionic strength under varying conditions of pH and sulphate ion concentration. The results have been collected in Table 1. The observed pseudo-first-order rate constants indicate that sulphate ion accelerates the rate of aquation of the oxalato complex. The rate accelerating effect of sulphate ion may be attributed to (1) the formation of reactive ionpairs such as $[(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4^+]SO_4^{2-}$ and $[(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}]SO_4^{2-}$, and (2) the existence of a HSO_4^- ion catalysed aquation path for the complex ion, $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}$. On this basis the scheme for aquation of the oxalato complex in the presence of SO_4^{2-} and H^+ ions may be represented as follows :

Consistent with the above scheme, the observed pseudo first order rate constant of aquation of the complex takes the form :

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_0K_1/[H^+] + k_1 + k_2[H^+] + (k_3K_2K_1/[H^+] + k_4K_3 + k_5[H^+]/K_4)[SO_4^{2-}]}{1 + K_1/[H^+] + (K_2K_1/[H^+] + K_3)[SO_4^{2-}]} \quad \dots (12)$$

Upon rearrangement Eq. (12) yields Eq. (13),

$$Y + k_{obs}(K_3 + K_1K_2/[H^+]) = k_3K_2K_1/[H^+] + k_4K_3 + k_5[H^+]/K_4 \quad \dots (13)$$

where

$$Y = \frac{k_{obs}(1 + K_1/[H^+]) - (k_0K_1/[H^+] + k_1 + k_2[H^+])}{[SO_4^{2-}]}$$

Neglecting the concentrations of $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}$ and the sulphate ionpairs, the concentrations of free sulphate and hydrogen ions corresponding to zero reaction time are given by the following relationships.

$$A[SO_4^{2-}]_{free}^2 + B[SO_4^{2-}]_{free} + C = 0 \quad \dots (14)$$

$$[H^+]_{free} = K_4[H^+]_{total}/(K_4 + [SO_4^{2-}]_{free}) \quad \dots (15)$$

where $A = 1 + K_5[Na^+]_{free}$, $B = K_4 + K_5K_4[Na^+]_{free} + [H^+]_{total} - [SO_4^{2-}]_{total}$, and $C = -K_4[SO_4^{2-}]_{total} - [SO_4^{2-}]_{free}$ and $[H^+]_{free}$ were computed from Eq. (14) and (15) respectively by substituting $[Na^+]_{free} = [Na^+]_{total}$ in the expression for A and B. The concentrations of sulphate and hydrogen ions being known, Eq. (12) was solved for k_3K_2 , k_4K_3 , k_5 , K_2 and K_3 using the best values of k_0 , k_1 , k_2 and K_1 obtained from the study of the acid hydrolysis of the complex¹⁰ in the absence of sulphate ion. The calculation was performed by means of a nonlinear least squares programme, adopted to the IBM 1130 computer, which varied the parameters and minimized the sum of the weighted residuals, $\Sigma[(k_{cal} - k_{obs})/\sigma(k_{obs})]^2$ where k_{obs} and k_{cal} stand for observed and calculated rate constants respectively and $\sigma(k_{obs})$ is the error of k_{obs} . The approximate values of K_2 and K_3 were guessed from the values of K_2 obtained from the study of the base hydrolysis of the oxalato complex in the presence of SO_4^{2-} ion at 30° and 40° and the values of the stability constants of the dicarboxylate ionpairs of $(NH_3)_5CoCl^{2+}$ reported by Monk *et al.*³. The approximate values of k_3K_2 ,

k_4K_3 and k_3 were obtained from $Y+k_{obs}(K_3+K_1K_2/[H^+])$ vs. $1/[H^+]$ and $Y+k_{obs}(K_3+K_1K_2/[H^+])$ vs $[H^+]$ plots respectively (Eq. (13)). The best fit values of the parameters have been collected in Table 1. The errors quoted for k_3 , k_4 and k_5 were estimated after fixing K_2 and K_3 at their best values. Similarly k_3 , k_4 and k_5 were taken to be constant in computing the errors of K_2 and K_3 .

The rate constants for the uncatalysed paths of aqutation of $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4^+$ and its protonated form are 2.68×10^{-6} and $1.38 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively at 66.1° and $0.3M$ ionic strength¹⁰. As against these, the rate constants for the aqutation of their sulphate ionpairs, under similar conditions of temperature and ionic strength, are 1.66×10^{-5} (k_3) and $2.06 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (k_4) respectively. Thus it is evident that the sulphate ionpairs react faster than the corresponding free complex ions. The catalytic effect of sulphate ion is much more pronounced on the k_0 path than on the k_1 path. This is indicated by the values of the ratios of the ionpair rate constant to the rate constant of the corresponding free complex ion ($k_3/k_0 \approx 6.2$ and $k_4/k_1 \approx 1.5$).

Oxygen exchange experiments by Andrade, Jordan and Taube¹³ and linear free energy correlation by Haim¹⁴ have indicated that k_0 and k_1 paths of aqutation of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex involve rate determining Co-O bond breaking process. As such ionpair like transition, states,

may be visualised for the k_0 and k_1 paths. The observed sequence : $k_4 > k_3 > k_1 > k_0$, points to the fact that such ionpair like transition states are more favourable for the substitution reactions of the sulphate ionpairs than for the free complex ions. In other words, the results indicate that SO_4^{2-} in the ionpairs repels the departing groups (i.e., $C_2O_4^{2-}$ and $C_2O_4H^-$) and decreases the electrostatic attraction between the leaving group and the Co(III) centre. Thus it is evident that the observed catalytic effect of SO_4^{2-} ion on the rate of aqutation of the oxalato complex provides additional evidence in support of the Co-O bond heterolysis mechanism for the k_0 , k_1 , k_3 and k_4 paths.

The rate constant (k_5) associated with the bisulphate ion catalysed path is found to be $9.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}M^{-1}$ at 66.1° and $0.3M$ ionic strength. Since the rate constant (k_2) for the proton catalysed path, under similar conditions, is $2.32 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}M^{-1}$ HSO_4^- ion appears to be more efficient in catalysing the aqutation of $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}$ than H^+ ion. The acid catalysed path of aqutation of $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}$ involves rapid protonation pre-equilibrium of the complex followed by rate determining loss of oxalic acid from the protonated species.

TABLE 1 -SULPHATE ION CATALYSED AQUTION OF $(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4^+$ AT 66.1° AND $\mu = 0.3M$

$k_0 = 2.68 \times 10^{-6} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $k_1 = 1.38 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $k_2 = 2.32 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}M^{-1}$, $K_1 = 1.86 \times 10^{-2}M$,
 $K_4 = 2.12 \times 10^{-2}M$ (calcd. from Ref 11), $K_5 = 1.01M^{-1}$ (calcd. from Ref. 12). Concn. of $[(NH_3)_5CoC_2O_4H^{2+}]_{total} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$

$[Na_2SO_4]$, (M)	$[H_2SO_4]$, (M)	$[HClO_4]$, (M)	$[NaClO_4]$, (M)	$[H^+]$, (M)	$[SO_4^{2-}]$, (M)	$10^5 k_{obs}^*$, sec^{-1}	$10^5 k_{cat}$, sec^{-1}
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
0.09	0.00	0.02	0.004	0.560×10^{-2}	6.21×10^{-2}	$1.08(\pm 0.03)$	1.12
0.075	0.00	0.05	0.019	1.92	3.61	$1.36(\pm 0.03)$	1.33
0.05	0.00	0.05	0.094	2.65	2.05	$1.33(\pm 0.03)$	1.30
0.10	0.00	0.05	0.00	1.50	5.24	$1.34(\pm 0.03)$	1.35
0.025	0.00	0.06	0.219	4.62	0.724	$1.27(\pm 0.04)$	1.32
0.05	0.00	0.00	0.144	0.070	3.91	$0.78(\pm 0.04)$	0.75
0.09	0.00	0.00	0.024	0.045	7.33	$0.94(\pm 0.02)$	0.94
0.05	0.00	0.10	0.044	6.55	1.18	$1.62(\pm 0.03)$	1.60
0.025	0.00	0.10	0.119	8.28	0.493	$1.53(\pm 0.03)$	1.52
0.025	0.00	0.05	0.169	3.72	0.839	$1.24(\pm 0.02)$	1.26
0.01	0.00	0.05	0.214	4.56	0.295	$1.25(\pm 0.03)$	1.21
0.00	0.05	0.00	0.244	6.62	1.14	$1.61(\pm 0.03)$	1.59
0.00	0.1	0.00	0.194	11.9	1.46	$2.07(\pm 0.04)$	2.10
0.00	0.15	0.00	0.144	17.0	1.63	$2.58(\pm 0.05)$	2.56
0.00	0.20	0.00	0.094	22.1	1.74	$2.98(\pm 0.05)$	2.99

$k_3 = 1.66(\pm 0.04) \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $k_4 = 2.06(\pm 0.06) \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $k_5 = 9.2(\pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}M^{-1}$,
 $K_2 = 11.6(\pm 0.6)M^{-1}$, $K_3 = 19.2(\pm 1.6)M^{-1}$, $\Sigma[(k_{cat} - k_{obs})/\sigma(k_{obs})]^2 = 10.0$

* Mean of triplicate runs. The errors quoted are average deviation from the mean.

It has been suggested earlier by Taube *et al.*¹³ that the protonated carbonyl function of the oxalato complex undergoes hydration and the resulting tetrahedral intermediate liberates oxalic acid with acyl cleavage (i.e., C-O bond fission). The polarizing power of the proton in HSO_4^- ion being much less than that of the proton, the former (i.e., HSO_4^-) would behave as a much weaker catalyst than the latter for the acyl cleavage process. Since the reverse is found to be true, it is presumed that acyl cleavage mechanism does not operate in the HSO_4^- ion catalysed path of aqutation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}$.

Alternatively the bisulphate ion catalysed path may be visualised in terms of the equilibrium pre-association of HSO_4^- with $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}$ followed by rate determining loss of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^-$ group from the ionpair with Co-O bond heterolysis.

Consistent with the above scheme k_5 is given by

$$k_5 = k(\text{HSO}_4^-)XQ \quad \dots (16)$$

The stability constant of the chloropentaammine-Cobalt(III) sulphate ionpair is about ten times higher than that of the chloropentaammine Cobalt(III) chloride and chloropentaammine Cobalt(III) acetate ionpairs ($Q(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoClSO}_4 = 20\text{M}^{-1}$, $Q(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoClCl}^+ = 2.6\text{M}^{-1}$, $Q(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoClAc}^+ = 1.3\text{M}^{-1}$ at 25° and $\mu_{\text{corr}} = 0.3\text{M}$ ref. (15)). The stability constant of $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}]\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ ionpair was found in the present work to be 11M^{-1} at 66.1° and $\mu = 0.3\text{M}$. As such it is reasonable to assume $Q = 1\text{M}^{-1}$ for the bisulphate ionpair under the experimental conditions of temperature and ionic strength. On this basis $k(\text{HSO}_4^-)$ turns out to be higher than the rate constant for the sulphate ion catalysed path. The sequence $k(\text{HSO}_4^-) > k_4$ ($k(\text{HSO}_4^-) = k_5/Q$) contradicts the expected influence of the charge of the ionpairing ligands (i.e., SO_4^{2-} and HSO_4^-) on the dissociative mode of activation of the sulphate and bisulphate ionpairs as well as the earlier findings of Monk *et al* and other workers¹⁻⁶ in connection with the uni- and bi-valent anion assisted aqutation of halopentaammine complexes of trivalent Cobalt and Chromium. Thus the observed sequence, $k_5 > k_2$, can not be reconciled with the ion pairing effect of HSO_4^- ion in the usual sense.

The possibility of proton transfer from bisulphate ion of the bisulphate ionpair to the departing $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^-$ group can not be ruled out in the $k(\text{HSO}_4^-)$ path. On this basis the transition state for the bisulphate ion catalysed path may be visualised as.

The leaving group being uncharged and the electrostatic interaction between the leaving group (i.e., $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}_2$) and the Co(III) centre in the activated state being annulled to some extent by the presence of SO_4^{2-} ion (which reduces the effective charge of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}^{3+}$ by ionpairing), it is reasonable to expect that the bisulphate ionpair will react faster than the sulphate ionpairs. Thus from the above considerations, it is apparent that HSO_4^- ion serves the roles of H^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions in catalysing the aqutation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}^{2+}$ and Co-O bond fission most likely occurs in the k_5 path.

Base Hydrolysis

The alkaline hydrolysis of oxalatopentaammine Cobalt(III) complex has been studied in the presence and absence of acetate, sulphate, carbonate, and phosphate ions in the medium of constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.3\text{M}$). The rate data have been collected in Table 2.

The general rate law for the base hydrolysis of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+$, observed by Jordan and Angerman¹⁶, is given by

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{11}[\text{OH}^-] + k'_{11}[\text{OH}^-]^2 \quad \dots (17)$$

where k_{11} and k'_{11} stand for the rate constants of Co-O and C-O bond fission paths respectively. At 35.2° and $\mu = 1.0\text{M}$ the values of k_{11} and k'_{11} reported by them are $14.6 \times 10^{-4}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$ and $1.9 \times 10^{-4}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-2}$ respectively. Since $k_{11} \gg k'_{11}$, it is reasonable to assume

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{11}[\text{OH}^-] \quad \dots (18)$$

as the rate law for the base hydrolysis of the complex at $[\text{OH}^-] < 0.1\text{M}$. In the present case, the base hydrolysis of the complex was studied at $[\text{OH}^-] < 0.1\text{M}$. The second order rate constants collected in Table 2 have been calculated assuming the rate law shown in Eq. (18). The values of k_{11} in the absence of anions were found to be $8.29 (\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-4}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$ and $5.30 (\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-3}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$ at 30° and 40° ($\mu = 0.3\text{M}$) respectively. Analogous rate constants computed from the data of Jordan *et al.*¹⁶ are $6.2 \times 10^{-4}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$ and $3.2 \times 10^{-3}\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$ at 30° and 40° ($\mu = 1.0\text{M}$) respectively. The discrepancies between our results and those obtained from the data of Jordan *et al.* reflects the retarding influence of ionic strength on the rate of base hydrolysis of the complex.

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that acetate ion in the range of concentration $0.05-0.25\text{M}$ does not influence the rate of base hydrolysis of the complex. SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , and PO_4^{3-} ions retard the same reaction. The observed second order rate constant ($k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{OH}^-]$) presented in Table 2 progressively decreases with increasing concentration of SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , and PO_4^{3-} . The rate data further indicate that the anions, under comparable conditions, retard the base hydrolysis of the complex in the order: $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CO}_3^{2-}$.

TABLE 2 -RATE DATA FOR THE BASE HYDROLYSIS OF $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+$

$\mu = 0.3M$

L^{n-}	$[\text{Na}_n\text{L}]$, (M)	$[\text{NaOH}]$, (M)	$10^3[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}\text{H}]$, (M)	$[\text{NaClO}_4]$, (M)	$k_{obs}, \text{sec}^{-1} \times 10^4$	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ [OH ⁻]	K_{ip}^{-1} , M
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$30.0(\pm 0.1)^\circ$							
SO_4^{2-}	0.01	0.05	2.32	0.22	3.77(±0.07)	7.91(±0.15)	0.073(±0.004)
	0.015	0.05	2.31	0.205	3.54(±0.11)	7.43(±0.23)	
	0.025	0.05	2.31	0.175	3.07(±0.06)	6.44(±0.12)	
	0.05	0.05	2.31	0.10	2.62(±0.04)	5.50(±0.08)	
	0.08	0.05	2.31	0.01	2.08(±0.08)	4.36(±0.17)	
$k_{11}^* = 8.29(\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-4} \text{sec}^{-1} \text{M}^{-1}$							
$40.3(\pm 0.1)^\circ$							
SO_4^{2-}	0.025	0.05	2.50	0.175	19.6(±0.6)	41.3(±1.2)	0.062(±0.005)
	0.50	0.05	2.41	0.100	17.1(±0.6)	35.9(±1.2)	
	0.08	0.05	2.50	0.010	11.5(±0.6)	24.2(±1.2)	
CO_3^{2-}	0.025	0.05	2.50	0.175	21.0(±0.5)	44.2(±1.0)	0.116(±0.011)
	0.05	0.05	2.50	0.100	18.5(±0.6)	38.9(±1.3)	
	0.08	0.05	2.50	0.010	15.5(±0.6)	32.6(±1.3)	
HPO_4^{2-}	0.005	0.06	2.46	0.19	27.0(±0.6)	51.4(±1.1)	0.028(±0.003)
	0.010	0.07	2.46	0.13	24.8(±0.6)	43.1(±1.0)	
	0.020	0.09	2.43	0.09	20.5(±0.5)	30.3(±0.7)	
CH_3CO_2^-	0.05	0.05	2.5	0.200	24.9(±0.5)	52.4(±1.0)	
	0.10	0.05	2.5	0.150	24.9(±0.6)	52.4(±1.3)	
	0.20	0.05	2.5	0.050	25.6(±0.5)	53.9(±1.0)	
	0.25	0.05	2.5	0.00	25.0(±0.5)	52.6(±1.0)	

$k_{11}^* = 53.0(\pm 1.2) \times 10^{-4} \text{sec}^{-1} \text{M}^{-1}$.

* Second order rate constant for the base hydrolysis of the complex in the absence of anions. Average of four runs at [OH⁻] = 0.05, 0.06, 0.09 and 0.1M.

Ascribing the observed retardation by the added ions to the slower rates of base hydrolysis of the ionpairs relative to that of the free complex ion, the reaction scheme may be represented as follows :

$\Downarrow K_{ip}$

Under pseudo-first-order conditions of hydroxide ion and anion concentrations, the rate law for the base hydrolysis of the complex is given by

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_{11} + (k_{11})_{ip} K_{ip} [\text{A}^{n-}]}{1 + K_{ip} [\text{A}^{n-}]} \quad \dots (19)$$

In the above equation k_{11} and $(k_{11})_{ip}$ stand for the second order rate constants for the base hydrolysis of the complex ion and its ionpair respectively and

K_{ip} is the stability constant of the ionpair Eq. (19) can easily be transformed to Eq. (20).

$$\frac{1}{k_{11} - k_{obs} / [\text{OH}^-]}$$

$$= \frac{1}{k_{11} - (k_{11})_{ip}} + \frac{1}{(k_{11} - (k_{11})_{ip}) K_{ip} [\text{A}^{n-}]} \quad \dots (20)$$

Representing the mole balance relationship for the total concentration of the anion as $[\text{A}^{n-}]_{total} = [\text{A}^{n-}] + [\text{Ionpair}] + [\text{NaA}^{(n-1)-}]$, it can be shown that

$$[\text{A}^{n-}] = \frac{[\text{A}^{n-}]_{total}}{1 + K_{ip} [(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4^+] + K_{ip} [\text{Na}^+]} \quad \dots (21)$$

where K_{ip}' stands for the stability constant of $\text{NaA}^{(n-1)-}$ species. In calculating the concentration of CO_3^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} ions corresponding to zero reaction time, the denominator of Eq. (21) was assumed to be $1 + K_{ip}' [\text{Na}^+]_{total}$. Such an assumption is reasonable since $[\text{A}^{n-}]_{total}$ was maintained at sufficiently high level as compared to $[\text{complex}]_{total}$, $[\text{Na}^+]_{total}$ was much higher than $[\text{A}^{n-}]_{total}$ and the values of

the stability constants of NaSO_4^- and NaCO_3^- ionpairs at the experimental temperatures and ionic strength are small (at 40° and $\mu = 0.3M$, $K'_{ip}(\text{NaSO}_4^-) = 1.07M^{-1}$ (calcd)¹²; $K'_{ip}(\text{NaCO}_3^-) = 0.52M^{-1}$ (calcd)¹⁷). The concentration of carbonate and sulphate ions so computed and the total concentration of phosphate fit Eq. (20) within the experimental errors of the rate constants. The calculated value of $1/(k_{11} - (k_{11})_{ip})$ in every case strikingly coincides with the experimental value of $1/k_{11}$. This means that the rate constants for the ionpairs are too small to be determined from the rate data. Assuming $(k_{11})_{ip} = 0$, the rate data were fitted to Eq. (20) by weighted least squares procedure. The values of $1/K'_{ip}$ so calculated have been incorporated in Table 2. These data indicate that the stabilities of the ionpairs follow the sequence : $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CO}_3^{2-}$.

Recent findings of Monk *et al.*³ reveal that the uncharged ionpairs of acetato pentaamminecobalt(III) undergo base hydrolysis at rates about 3-5 times slower than acetatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex. In the present work, the anionic ionpairs of oxalato-pentaamminecobalt(III) with PO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-} , and CO_3^{2-} are found to be inert towards base hydrolysis. The inertness of the ionpairs is consistent with SN_1CB mechanism¹⁶ for their base hydrolysis reaction. According to SN_1CB mechanism, the ratio of the rate constant of the ionpair to the free ion is given by

$$(k_{11})_{ip}/k_{11} = (k'_{CB}/k_{CB}) \times K'_{CB}/K_{CB}$$

where K_{CB} , K'_{CB} and k_{CB} , k'_{CB} stand for the forward equilibrium quotient for the conjugate bases and the rate constant of release of oxalate from the conjugate bases in dissociative paths respectively.

k'_{CB} is expected to be greater than k_{CB} since the conjugate base of the ionpair is negatively charged. The inertness of the ionpairs, according to C.B. mechanism, would, therefore, be ascribed to $K'_{CB} \ll K_{CB}$. This again is consistent with the effect of the overall charge of the free and ionpaired complex on their conjugate base equilibria as depicted above.

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